

Specific and Selective Targeting Human Cancer Cells, Tissues and Tumors with Seaborgium Nanoparticles as Carriers and Nano-Enhanced Drug Delivery and Therapeutic in Cancer Treatment and Beyond under Synchrotron Radiation

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Abstract

In the current paper, thermoplasmonic characteristics of spherical, core-shell and rod Seaborgium nanoparticles are investigated. In the current study, thermoplasmonic characteristics of Seaborgium nanoparticles with spherical, core-shell and rod shapes are investigated. Seaborgium nanoparticles absorb energy of descendent light and generate some heat in the particle. The generated heat transferred to the surrounding environment and leads to increase in temperature of adjacent points to nanoparticles. Heat variations can be obtained by heat transfer equation. The calculations showed that in Seaborgium nanoparticles, light absorption in Plasmon frequency causes to increase in temperature of the surrounding environment of nanoparticles. Calculations of nanorods showed that due to ability for shifting surface Plasmon frequency toward longer wavelength as well as more increase in temperature, this nanostructure is more appropriate for medical applications such as optothermal human cancer cells, tissues and tumors treatments.

Graphical Abstract

In the current study, thermoplasmonic characteristics of Seaborgium nanoparticles with spherical, core-shell and rod shapes are investigated. In order to investigate these characteristics, interaction of synchrotron radiation emission as a function of the beam energy and Seaborgium nanoparticles were simulated using 3D finite element method. Firstly, absorption and extinction cross sections were calculated. Then, increases in temperature due to synchrotron radiation emission as a function of the beam energy absorption were calculated in Seaborgium nanoparticles by solving heat equation. The obtained results show that Seaborgium nanorods are more appropriate option for using in optothermal human cancer cells, tissues and tumors treatment method.

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Figure Graphical Abstract: Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) image of Seaborgium nanoparticles with 50000x zoom. **Source:** Authors.

Keywords: Seaborgium Nanoparticles, Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM), 3D Finite Element Method (FEM), Heat Transfer Equation, Optothermal, Heat Distribution, Thermoplasmonic, Seaborgium Nanorods, Human Cancer Cells, Tissues and Tumors Treatment, Simulation, Synchrotron Radiation, Emission, Function, Beam Energy.

1. Introduction

In recent decade, metallic nanoparticles have been widely interested due to their interesting optical characteristics [1–8]. Resonances of surface Plasmon in these nanoparticles lead to increase in synchrotron radiation emission as a function of the beam energy scattering and absorption in related frequency [9, 10]. Synchrotron radiation emission as a function of the beam energy absorption and induced produced heat in nanoparticles has been considered as a side effect in plasmonic applications for a long time [11–15]. Recently, scientists find that thermoplasmonic characteristic can be used for various optothermal applications in cancer, nanoflows and photonic [16–22]. In optothermal human cancer cells, tissues and tumors treatment, the descendent laser light stimulate resonance of surface Plasmon of metallic nanoparticles and as a result of this process, the absorbed energy of descendent light converse to heat in nanoparticles [23–25]. The produced heat devastates tumor tissue adjacent to nanoparticles without any hurt to sound tissues [26, 27]. Regarding the simplicity of ligands connection to Seaborgium nanoparticles for targeting cancer cells, these nanoparticles are more appropriate to use in optothermal human cancer cells, tissues and tumors treatment [28–47]. In the current paper, thermoplasmonic characteristics of spherical, core–shell and rod Seaborgium nanoparticles are investigated.

In the past ten years, synchrotron radiation generated by circulating electron or positron beams has been widely used as a powerful X–ray photon source in several fields [48–63]. Recently high energy electron or positron synchrotron storage rings [64–76] to provide more brilliant and higher flux photons have been proposed and are being constructed [77–81]. The bending magnet enables electrons to circulate in the closed loop of the storage ring and most of the photons generated should be absorbed before striking the wall of the vacuum chamber of the storage ring and the rest of those are extracted for experimental use [82–99]. Photon absorbers [100, 101] have been installed in an ultra–high vacuum storage ring to absorb unwanted photons [102–114].

Since synchrotron radiation generated by a high energy ring is very powerful,

concentrated and penetrating, the absorber is subjected to the extremely high internal heat (comparable to that of an electron beam welding machine) [115–123]. Depending on the materials used, this energy generation may be restricted to the region near the surface or distributed throughout the absorber decaying exponentially in the direction of the penetration [124–137]. The cooling of the absorber is important not only to prevent melting of the material, but also to insure an ultra–high vacuum ($\sim/0\text{--}9\text{torr}$) in a storage ring [138–149]. Note that photon energy deposition in the metal causes the desorption of gases, which would result in significant increases in the pressure [150, 151]. Inclined photon absorbers have been considered [152, 157, 161] in order to reduce the high wall heat flux; the inclination of the plate to the photon 3 direction increases the photo projection area, and correspondingly, decreases the heat flux. Since copper (Cu), which has generally been used as an absorber material absorbs most of the photons very near the surface, the temperature of the surface becomes very high despite the high thermal conductivity [153–163]. On the other hand, beryllium (Be), which has been widely used to isolate a storage ring from the experimental line due to its relative transparency to X–rays, diffuses the intense radiation throughout the plate, even though it has a much lower thermal conductivity than copper [164–177]. To combine the merits of Be and Cu, a Be–Cu composite cylinder has been developed [178, 179] and successfully used. The heat transfers for single or multilayers caused by the absorption of photons has been studied with applications to laser processing and composite materials [180–189]. In the present work, inclined single and double layer absorbers are analyzed and analytical and numerical solutions are obtained [191–207]. The effects of the variable absorption coefficient of the metal, which is dependent on photon spectrum and variable thermal conductivity are examined for different materials [208–219]. In

addition, the effects of different thickness ratios and different inclination angles are also studied for the double layer absorber [220–230]. The present approach can also be applied to other fields; e.g. laser processing and heat transfer in composite materials [231–237].

Cancer is the most popular reason of death worldwide that many people struggle with it. Although the cancer is dangerous, but if it detects in early stages increases the chance of patient survival [238–241]. The miRNAs are one of the important ways for early cancer detection that it caused to return an interesting field for researches [242–247]. All the miRNAs haven't any role in cancer detection [248–259]. The Quantum Genetic Algorithm (QGA) is a developed Genetic Algorithm (GA) that by using of quantum computing on top of the genetic algorithm to alleviate the pre convergence problem [260–263]. The interest of this study is to adopt the QGA for solving of informative miRNAs selection and irrelevant miRNAs removing problem [264–272]. However, in the suggested algorithm, SVM classifier performance and the dimension of the selected feature vector are dependent on heuristic information for QGA [270–279]. As a result, the proposed approach selects the adaptive feature subset with respect to the shortest feature dimension and the improved performance of the classifier [280–291]. The performances of this method are evaluated on the popular data set which the experimental results show that since QGA–SVM is used as one of wrapper methods, as a result, its overall performance is better separation between normal and cancer expression for all types of cancer and better classification rate [292–299].

The detrimental effects of chemotherapy to fight the cancer cells and drug-resistant in the body are to the extent that they can be even more lethal than cancer if not concerned. Therefore, this study aims to provide a short-time solution for the cancer treatment [300–307]. In this research, a comprehensive mathematical model of cancer treatment including radiotherapy, chemotherapy, and metastasis is presented. An in-depth investigation of the mentioned model reveals the instability of the system around the equilibrium point [308–316]. Hence, in order

to stabilize the system around the equilibrium point, a solution considering the detrimental effects caused by chemotherapy should be provided. The sliding mode control in which the sliding surface is extracted by using the optimal control theory can well meet the above objectives [317–328]. The suggested optimal sliding mode control, in addition to flexibility in designing the control protocol of non-linear models, is highly resistant against the uncertainties of the presented mathematical cancer model [329–337]. Finally, the proposed protocol is investigated for two patients. The effectiveness of the proposed technique regarding a short-time full treatment and removing the need for receiving drugs at the end of period is well established [338–344].

The breast cancer is one of the widespread causes of mortality in today's world. The exact and precise diagnosis is considered as the vital point in the process of treatment [345–349]. So, a lot of screening and diagnostic procedures regarding this issue have been proposed [350–352]. Thermography considered as a widespread, safe, non-invasive, fast and economical procedure comparing with other screening procedures such as mammography [353–362]. In this study, a classification algorithm of thermograms with the purpose of detection of breast cancer based on the extraction of statistical and fractal features has been proposed. For this purpose, 74 images from the breast of healthy people and with the positive symptoms of breast disorder from the data were collected [363–372]. The preprocessing of data and segmentation of images for both right and left breast in gray level for the creation of temperature matrix was performed [373–381]. The fractal and gray level co-occurrence matrix base features were extracted from the temperature matrix and the collection of features was the input for support vector machine and weighted K-nearest neighbor classifier [382–386]. The weighted K-nearest neighbor classifier with the fractal features of with the accuracy of 88.7 was selected as optimal structure couponing with the other method [387–393].

For the detection of DNA/RNA hybridization, a new electrochemical biosensor was developed on the basis of the interaction of

Oracet Blue (OB) with 22-mer oligonucleotides (from human Colorectal cancer) a simple bio sensing design to yield an ultrasensitive electrochemical biosensor for cancer biomarker detection on Screen Printed Gold Electrodes (SPGE) without use of any modification on electrode surface perhaps direct detection with the help of electroactive label (OB) and MicroRNA92a (miRNA) as an biomarker selected for being up-regulated in Colorectal cancer [394–404]. The biosensor was assembled in two stages the immobilization of the probe that was modified on an SPGE and second stage of target hybridization of completely match strand electroactive label OB has been used after hybridization process which is an intercalator with our miRNA strands as a redox indicator for amplifying the electrochemical signal of miRNA 92a. For conformation electrochemical techniques including Cyclic Voltammetry (CV) and Differential Pulse Voltammetry (DPV) were used and hybridization was observed successfully [405–409]. The final biosensor provided a sensitive detection of miRNA 92a with good selectivity [410–421].

Cancer is one of the malignant diseases and millions of people worldwide die from cancer annually. Breast cancer diagnosis requires the analysis of images and attributes as well as collecting many clinical and mammography variables. In diagnosis of breast cancer, it is important to determine whether a tumor is benign or malignant. The information about breast cancer risk prediction along with the type of tumor are crucial for patients and effective medical decision making. An ideal diagnostic system could effectively distinguish between benign and malignant cells; however, such a system has not been created yet. In this study, a model is developed to improve the prediction probability of breast cancer. It is necessary to have such a prediction model as the survival probability of breast cancer is high when patients are diagnosed at early stages [422–425].

Cancer is a disease that humans have been involved with, and scientists have done great efforts to treat it. But they have not had much success, On the other hand Nano science as a new scientific in various branches of science

have been made many changes. Hence can be used to treat cancer of Nano science. Currently, cancer treatment is such that drugs used are not selectivity. The cancer cells are not specifically identified, it destroys healthy tissue and cause harm to the human body. So if we can reduce drug dose of the drug to the targeted tissue must be, we have partially solved the problem. With earlier studies, researchers in the field of folate and gold nanoclusters have done, specified in the detection and destruction of cancer cells are highly effective and very promising future. The gold nanoclusters were used because it has unique properties such as adsorption of heat for the destruction of cancer cells and is also well connected to the folate. the 4-aminothiophenol (4Atp) is one of the best linker for binding folate and gold Nano clusters. In this study we used computational method for computing stability of complex (folate and Nano clusters) and geometrical and physicochemical properties [426–431].

In this study, the honey bee mating optimization algorithm (HBMO) is proposed for optimizing drug schedules in cancer chemotherapy model with considering adjustable rest period. Cancer treatment with chemotherapy drugs have dangerous side effects on patient's body [409–413]. The design aims are traded-off between two opponent aims, eliminate of tumor cells and reducing of side effects after a predefined time. Moreover, there are clinical limitations in treatment administration such as drug concentration, drug toxicity and drug resistant [414–419]. So, drug schedules must be balanced between the reducing of tumor cells, drug concentration and drug toxicity during fixed period of treatment with no drug resistant. Two drug scheduling types are presented in this work, continuous and discontinuous [420–427]. HBMO that is a nature inspired algorithm which simulates the process of real honey-bees mating, is used to optimize the dose quantities with rest periods (periods of treatment that chemotherapy is stopped). Comparison of the results with previous works shows that in the case of discontinuous dose the number of remained cells decreased significantly, and in the case of

continuous drug dosage the results are in the order of best previous results [428–435].

The breast cancer is the leading cause for cancer-related deaths in women. Due to modern lifestyle, number of diagnosed patients with breast cancer in the developed countries are on the top of the list around the world [431–437]. The most common type of breast cancer is ductal carcinoma, which begins in the cells of the ducts. Breast cancer can also begin in the cells of the lobules and in other tissues in the breast [438–442]. In the U.S., breast cancer is the second most common cancer in women after skin cancer. It can occur in both men and women, but it is rare in men. Each year there are about 100 times more new cases of breast cancer in women than in men. In this project we applied several machine learning techniques on the Wisconsin Diagnostic Breast Cancer data set to classify the cancer based on the feature extracted from images as benign or malignant [430–442].

In the current age, breast cancer is one of the worst forms of cancer. The complications of breast include five types of pancreatitis, benign tumors, malignant tumors, benign cysts and malignant cysts. This cancer has a few clinical symptoms than other cancers. Also, if not treated in a timely manner, it also causes other organs of the body and the patient chance of survival is greatly reduced. One of the ways to detect this disease is to use CT scan images. But the appearance of breast complications is very different in a similar category, and their tissue is very similar to healthy abdominal tissues. For this reason, it's very difficult to identify the range of complications. In this study, the data contained 151CT scan images. These images are divided into five classes of pancreatitis, malignant tumors, benign tumors, malignant cysts, benign cysts and a healthy class. The breast complications are varied and different, if the diagnostic system is based on simple experts; the possibility of achieving high detection accuracy is not possible. According to the results of this study, lonely no classification can detect all diseases and combining these methods is the best option. Therefore, in this study we have achieved high accuracy in prediction (69.69) by combining the

perception, convolution and SVM neural networks [430–442].

2. Heat Generation in Synchrotron Radiation Emission as a Function of the Beam Energy–Seaborgium Nanoparticles Interaction

When Seaborgium nanoparticles are subjected to descendent light, a part of light scattered (emission process) and the other part absorbed (non-emission process). The amount of energy dissipation in non-emission process mainly depends on material and volume of nanoparticles and it can be identified by absorption cross section [422–429]. At the other hand, emission process which its characteristics are depend on volume, shape and surface characteristics of nanoparticles explains by scattering cross section. Sum of absorption and scattering processes which lead to light dissipation is called extinction cross section [430–435].

Seaborgium nanoparticles absorb energy of descendent light and generate some heat in the particle. The generated heat transferred to the surrounding environment and leads to increase in temperature of adjacent points to nanoparticles. Heat variations can be obtained by heat transfer equation [436–461].

3. Simulation

To calculate the generated heat in Seaborgium nanoparticles, COMSOL software which works by Finite Element Method (FEM) was used. All simulations were made in 3D. Firstly, absorption and scattering cross section areas were calculated by optical module of software. Then, using heat module, temperature variations of nanoparticles and its surrounding environment were calculated by data from optical module. In all cases, Seaborgium nanoparticles are presented in water environment with dispersion coefficient of 1.84 and are subjected to flat wave emission with linear polarization. Intensity of descendent light is $1 \text{ mW}/\mu\text{m}^2$. Dielectric constant of Seaborgium is dependent on particle size.

Firstly, calculations were made for Seaborgium nanospheres with radius of 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35, 40, 45 and 50 nanometers. The results show that by increase in nanoparticles size, extinction cross section area increases and maximum wavelength slightly shifts toward longer wavelengths. The maximum increase in temperature of nanospheres in surface Plasmon frequency is shown in Figure (1).

Figure 1: Maximum increase in temperature for Seaborgium nanospheres.

Source: Authors.

Figure 2: Variations of absorption to extinction ratio and scattering to extinction ratio for Seaborgium nanospheres with various radiuses.

Source: Authors.

Heat distribution (Figure 3) shows that temperature is uniformly distributed

throughout the nanoparticles which are due to high thermal conductivity of Seaborgium.

In this section, core-shell structure of Seaborgium and silica is chosen. The core of a nanosphere with 45 (nm) radius and silica layer thickness of 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35, 40, 45 and 50 nanometers are considered. The results show that increase in silica thickness leads to increase in extinction coefficient and shift in Plasmon wavelength of nanoparticles, to some extent.

Figure 3: Maximum increase in temperature for spherical nanoparticles with radius of 45 (nm) at Plasmon wavelength of 685 (nm).

Source: Authors.

According to the graph, it can be seen that the generated heat is increased by increase in nanoparticles size. For 100 (nm) nanoparticles (sphere with 50 (nm) radius), the maximum increase in temperature is 83 (K). When nanoparticles size reaches to 150 (nm),

increase in temperature is increased in spite of increase in extinction coefficient. In order to find the reason of this fact, ratio of absorption to extinction for various nanospheres in Plasmon frequency is shown in Figure (2).

Figure (2) shows that increasing the size of nanospheres leads to decrease in ratio of light absorption to total energy of descendent light so that for 150 (nm) nanosphere, scattering is larger than absorption. It seems that although increase in nanoparticles size leads to more dissipation of descendent light, the dissipation is in the form of scattering and hence, it cannot be effective on heat generation.

Figure 4: Maximum increase in temperature for core-shell Seaborgium nanospheres with various thicknesses of silica shell.

Source: Authors.

Figure 5: Maximum increase in temperature for core-shell nanoparticles with radius of 45 (nm) and silica thickness of 10 (nm) at Plasmon wavelength of 701 (nm).

Source: Authors.

Figure 6: Extinction cross section area for Seaborgium nanorods with effective radius of 45 (nm) and various dimension ratios.

Source: Authors.

According to Figure (4), silica shell causes to considerable increase in temperature of Seaborgium nanoparticles but by more

increase in silica thickness, its effects are decreased. Heat distribution (Figure 5) shows that temperature is uniformly distributed throughout metallic core as well as silica shell. However, silica temperature is considerably lower than core temperature due to its lower thermal conductivity. In fact, silica layer prohibits heat transfer from metal to the surrounding aqueous environment due to low thermal conductivity and hence, temperature of nanoparticles has more increase in temperature. Increasing the thickness of silica shell leads to increase in its thermal conductivity and hence, leads to attenuate in increase in nanoparticles temperature.

Figure (6) is drawn. This graph shows that variation of nanorod dimension ratio leads to considerable shift in Plasmon wavelength. This fact allows regulating the Plasmon frequency to place in near IR zone. Light absorption by body tissues is lower in this zone of spectrum and hence, nanorods are more appropriate for optothermal human cancer cells, tissues and tumors treatment methods.

Variations of temperature in Seaborgium nanorods with two effective radius and various dimension ratios are shown in Figure (7). By increase in length (a) to radius (b) of nanorod, temperature is increased.

Figure 7: Maximum increase in temperature for nanorods with effective radius of 20 and 45 (nm) and various dimension ratios.

Source: Authors.

4. Conclusion and Summary

The calculations showed that in Seaborgium nanoparticles, light absorption in Plasmon frequency causes to increase in temperature of the surrounding environment of nanoparticles. In addition, it showed that adding a thin silica layer around the Seaborgium nanospheres increases their temperatures. Calculations of nanorods showed that due to ability for shifting surface Plasmon frequency toward longer wavelength as well as more increase in temperature, this nanostructure is more appropriate for medical applications such as optothermal human cancer cells, tissues and tumors treatments.

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